

Computational Solutions for Systematic Literature Review Conduction Support in Software Engineering: A Systematic Mapping

Maria Fernanda de Abreu Aguiar, Érica Ferreira de Souza, Katia Romero Felizardo

Federal University of Technology – Paraná, Cornélio Procópio, PR – Brazil

mariaaguiar@alunos.utfpr.edu.br, ericasouza@utfpr.edu.br, katiascannavino@utfpr.edu.br

Luciana B. R. dos Santos

Gran Sasso Science Institute (GSSI), L'Aquila – Italy

luciana.rebelo@gssi.it

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Table 1: List of related works

ID	Title	Year	Reference
1	Towards the Use of AI-Based Tools for Systematic Literature Review	2024	[33]
2	Simulation-based Active Learning for Systematic Reviews: A Systematic Review of the Literature	2023	[36]
3	Artificial intelligence to automate the systematic review of scientific literature	2023	[6]
4	Challenges in identifying studies to include in a systematic literature review: an analysis of the organizational growth and decline topics	2023	[5]
5	Automating Systematic Literature Reviews with Natural Language Processing and Text Mining: A Systematic Literature Review	2023	[35]
6	Towards a Maturity Model for Systematic Literature Review Process	2022	[7]
7	Automation of systematic literature reviews: A systematic literature review	2021	[38]
8	Automated Support for Searching and Selecting Evidence in Software Engineering: A Cross-domain Systematic Mapping	2021	[23]
9	Systematic Literature Review Tools: Are we there yet?	2021	[39]
10	Adoption of Machine Learning Techniques to Perform Secondary Studies: A Systematic Mapping Study for the Computer Science Field	2021	[4]
11	Semi-automated Tools for Systematic Searches	2021	[1]
12	Tool support for systematic literature reviews : analyzing existing solutions and the potential for automation	2021	[15]
13	Systematic review and meta-analysis: processes towards selection automation	2021	[14]
14	Analysis of the Tools to Support Systematic Literature Review in Software Engineering	2021	[34]
15	Crowdsourcing in Systematic Reviews: A Systematic Mapping and Survey	2020	[9]
16	Conducting a Systematic Review: Trends in Machine Learning and Text Mining	2020	[8]
17	Systematic review automation methods	2020	[25]
18	Identification and prioritization of SLR search tool requirements: an SLR and a survey	2019	[2]
19	Guidelines for Maintaining Systematic Literature Reviews in Software Engineering	2019	[24]
20	Study on automatic citation screening in systematic reviews: reporting, reproducibility and complexity	2019	[27]
21	Automated Selection and Quality Assessment of Primary Studies: A Systematic Literature Review	2019	[31]
22	(Automated) literature analysis: threats and experiences	2018	[32]
23	Improving Systematic Literature Review with Automation and Bibliometrics	2018	[30]

ID	Title	Year	Reference
24	Tool features to support systematic reviews in software engineering-a cross domain study	2018	[18]
25	Supporting systematic literature reviews in computer science: the systematic literature review toolkit	2018	[11]
26	Text-Mining Techniques and Tools for Systematic Literature Reviews: A Systematic Literature Review	2017	[10]
27	On the pragmatic design of literature studies in software engineering: an experience-based guideline	2017	[17]
28	Vision for SLR tooling infrastructure: prioritizing value-added requirements	2017	[3]
29	Reproducibility of studies on text mining for citation screening in systematic reviews: Evaluation and checklist	2017	[28]
30	Identification of SLR tool needs - Results of a community workshop	2016	[12]
31	Tool support for systematic reviews in software engineering	2016	[19]
32	A critical analysis of studies that address the use of text mining for citation screening in systematic reviews	2016	[26]
33	How to Read Less: Better Machine Assisted Reading Methods for Systematic Literature Reviews	2016	[40]
34	Beyond the spreadsheet: reflections on tool support for literature studies	2016	[37]
35	Tools to support systematic reviews in software engineering: A cross-domain survey using semi-structured interviews	2015	[22]
36	Using text mining for study identification in systematic reviews: a systematic review of current approaches	2015	[29]
37	Tools to Support Systematic Literature Reviews in Software Engineering: A Mapping Study	2015	[20]
38	Outcomes of a community workshop to identify and rank barriers to the systematic literature review process	2014	[13]
39	Tools to support systematic reviews in software engineering: a feature analysis	2014	[21]
40	Refining the systematic literature review process-two participant-observer case studies	2010	[16]

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